

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES INCLUDING STRAIN RATE EFFECT

J. F. Chen, E. V. Morozov*, K. Shankar
 School of Engineering and Information Technology,
 University of New South Wales, Canberra, Australia
 * Corresponding author (e.morozov@adfa.edu.au)

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1 Introduction

There are wide applications of fibre reinforced composite materials in the aerospace structures, marine engineering, civil infrastructures, etc. In many of these applications, the progressive failure analysis is required to predict the mechanical behaviour of composite structures. Experimental studies have shown that some composite materials may exhibit apparent plastic response and degradation of their properties. A combined elastoplastic damage model considering these effects has been developed for composite laminates and discussed in [1]. Some composite structural elements could also be subjected to dynamic loading and composite materials may exhibit strain rate-dependent mechanical behaviour. For example, carbon fibre reinforced composites AS4/3501-6 and AS4/PEEK have demonstrated strain rate sensitivity under various loadings according to experimental investigations [2, 3]. The progressive failure analysis of composite materials requires a development of an appropriate material constitutive model to characterise and represent their complex mechanical behaviour, including various in-plane failure modes, irreversible deformations, strain rate effects and damage initiation and progression.

Continuum damage mechanics (CDM) provides a tractable framework for the simulation of progressive failure of materials. Several composite material models including strain rate effects have been developed based on CDM [4-8]. A few of them [4, 5] were developed using viscous regularisation of Perzyna type [9] to accommodate strain rate-dependent plasticity and damage effects in the rate-independent elastoplastic damage material models. In viscoplasticity models based on viscous regularisation of Perzyna type, rate-independent

plastic yield functions are used for describing viscoplastic strains. Upon viscoplastic loading, a stress state could be located outside the yield surface. As a result, the Kuhn-Tucker plastic loading/unloading conditions and the plastic consistency condition could not be satisfied. Thus, the rate-dependent solution to a viscoplastic problem using Perzyna type viscous regularisation could not be directly obtained based on a return mapping algorithm, which is numerically efficient but requires that the plastic stress state be “corrected” to remain on the yield surface upon viscoplastic loading. Instead, a return mapping algorithm can be used to obtain the solution to the rate-independent plastic problem first. Then, an additional algorithm can be developed to convert this solution to the rate-dependent solution to the viscoplastic problem [10]. Alternatively, the rate-dependent solution to a viscoplastic problem of the Perzyna type could be found using explicit schemes, such as forward Euler method [5], or iterative methods in which the duration of the iterative process is governed by the condition when the sum of the time subsegments reaches the size of the current time step [4, 11]. Hufner and Accorsi [6] proposed a progressive failure model for woven composites with a strain rate-dependent yield criterion to describe their viscoplasticity effects. The model has been implemented using an explicit integration algorithm. Huang et al. [7] also developed an elasto-viscoplastic damage model employing Weeks and Sun’s modified Johnson-Cook strain rate-dependent yield criterion [3], which required values of the state variables from a reference state (e.g. quasi-static state), to consider the strain rate effects on the plasticity behaviour of composites. The influence of strain rate on the evolution of damage was considered by the Perzyna type viscous

regularisation of the damage thresholds. For the viscoplasticity models employing strain rate-dependent yield criteria, upon viscoplastic loading, a stress state is permissible only when it lies on the yield surface. In this case, the Kuhn-Tucker loading/unloading conditions and the plastic consistency condition remain valid. Hence, robust and efficient implicit numerical integration procedures (such as return mapping algorithms), which are unconditionally stable and allow large time steps to be used when computational convergence rate is good, could be developed for these models. A model based on such an approach was called a consistency viscoplastic model by Wang et al. [12]. According to their work, the consistency model was generally more computationally efficient than the Perzyna type viscoplastic model.

Although attempts have been made to include viscoplasticity effects in CDM-based models, very little work has been undertaken to develop viscoplastic damage models based on strain rate-dependent yield functions, especially, in conjunction with implicit numerical integration algorithms.

In this study, an elasto-viscoplastic damage model allowing for plasticity, the strain rate effects and post-failure progressive damage development in composite laminates subjected to various strain rate loadings is proposed. Thiruppukuzhi and Sun's strain rate-dependent yield criterion [13] is adopted to define the rate-dependent plastic yield surface. The use of this criterion ensures that the Kuhn-Tucker plastic loading/unloading conditions and plastic consistency condition remain valid for the present viscoplastic model. A damage model is employed to take into account the post-failure progressive degradation of material stiffness. An appropriate strain-driven implicit integration algorithm is developed using equations of continuum damage mechanics, plasticity theory and return mapping procedure. To ensure the algorithmic efficiency of the Newton-Raphson method in the finite element analysis, a tangent stiffness operator consistent with the developed integration algorithm has been derived and implemented.

2 Consistency elasto-viscoplastic damage model

2.1 Stress-strain relationship

The consistency elasto-viscoplastic damage model is developed for an elementary orthotropic ply. The

model accounts for the plastic response, strain rate effects, and progressive degradation of material stiffness. The plasticity and strain rate effects are represented using viscoplasticity theory. The damage effects are considered by introducing damage variables in the stiffness tensor based on the continuum damage mechanics approach. According to this, the stress-strain relationships for the undamaged and damaged composite materials are presented in the following forms, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} &= \mathbf{S}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e = \mathbf{S}_0 : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p); \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} &= \mathbf{S}(d) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e = \mathbf{S}(d) : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p)\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where bold-face symbols are used for variables of tensorial character and symbol $(:)$ denotes inner product of two tensors with double contraction, e.g. $(\mathbf{S}(d) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e)_{ij} = S(d)_{ijkl} \varepsilon_{kl}^e$, where the summation convention is applied to the subscripts; $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ are the Cauchy nominal stress tensor and the effective stress tensor (both are of the second order); \mathbf{S}_0 is the fourth-order constitutive tensor for linear-elastic undamaged unidirectional laminated composite; $\mathbf{S}(d)$ is the one for the associated damaged material. The explicit form of \mathbf{S}_0 is determined by elasticity theory for orthotropic materials; $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$ are the total strain, elastic strain, and plastic strain tensors, respectively; d is the damage variable.

In finite element implementations, it is more convenient to use Voigt notation [14] to convert higher order symmetric tensors to lower order matrices. The Voigt form of the fourth order tensor $\mathbf{S}(d)$ adopted in this model is similar to that presented by Matzenmiller et al. [15], i.e.

$$\mathbf{S}(d) = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1 - d_1)E_1^0 & B\nu_{21}^0 E_1^0 & 0 \\ B\nu_{12}^0 E_1^0 & (1 - d_2)E_2^0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D(1 - d_3)G_{12}^0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{S}(d)$ (printed in *italic*) is used to identify the Voigt form of $\mathbf{S}(d)$; $D = 1 - (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)\nu_{12}^0\nu_{21}^0$; parameter $B = (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)$; parameters d_1 , d_2 , d_3 denote damage developed in the fibre and transverse direction, and under shear (these damage variables are constant throughout the ply thickness); E_1^0 , E_2^0 , G_{12}^0 and ν_{12}^0 , ν_{21}^0 are elastic moduli and Poisson's ratios of the undamaged unidirectional composite laminate, respectively.

In order to take into account the different effects of compression and tension on the failure modes, the

damage variables are introduced as follows:

$$d_1 = \begin{cases} d_{1t} & \text{if } \bar{\sigma}_1 \geq 0 \\ d_{1c} & \text{if } \bar{\sigma}_1 < 0 \end{cases} \quad d_2 = \begin{cases} d_{2t} & \text{if } \bar{\sigma}_2 \geq 0 \\ d_{2c} & \text{if } \bar{\sigma}_2 < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where d_{1t} , d_{1c} characterise the damage development caused by tension and compression in the fibre direction, and d_{2t} , d_{2c} reflect the damage development caused by tension and compression in the transverse direction, respectively; $\bar{\sigma}_1$, $\bar{\sigma}_2$ are the effective stresses in the fibre and transverse directions.

It is assumed that the shear stiffness reduction results from the fibre and matrix cracking. To take this into account, the corresponding damage variable d_3 is expressed as:

$$d_3 = 1 - (1 - d_6)(1 - d_{1t}) \quad (4)$$

where d_6 represents the damage effects on shear stiffness caused by matrix cracking.

2.2 Viscoplasticity model

Plasticity is assumed to occur in the undamaged area of the composites under load. The strain rate-dependent plastic behaviour of composite materials in the undamaged area is modelled by the following equation:

$$F(\bar{\sigma}, \bar{\varepsilon}^p, \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p) = F^p(\bar{\sigma}) - \kappa(\bar{\varepsilon}^p, \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p) = 0 \quad (5)$$

where F and F^p are the plastic yield function and the plastic potential, respectively; κ is the hardening parameter, which depends on the plastic deformations and is strain rate-dependent; it is expressed in terms of equivalent plastic strain $\bar{\varepsilon}^p$ and equivalent plastic strain rate $\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p$.

The plastic potential has the same form as in the original model [1] and is given by

$$F^p(\bar{\sigma}) = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (\bar{\sigma}_2^2 + 2a \bar{\sigma}_3^2)} \quad (6)$$

where a is a material-characteristic constant which describes the different level of plasticity developed under shear loading compared to the transverse loading; $\bar{\sigma}_3$ is the effective shear stress.

A power law accounting for the strain rate-dependent hardening behaviour is expressed as follows [13]

$$\kappa(\bar{\varepsilon}^p, \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p) = \tilde{\sigma}(\bar{\varepsilon}^p, \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p) = \left(\frac{\bar{\varepsilon}^p}{\chi(\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p)^{m^*}} \right)^{\frac{1}{n^*}} \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}$ is the equivalent stress, χ , m^* and n^* are coefficients that define the strain rate-dependent hardening curve and are determined from experiments. According to experimental results, the parameters a and n^* are rate-independent [13]. These two parameters are determined using an approach based on the linear regression analyses of the off-axis tensile tests performed on the unidirectional composite specimens subjected to a constant total strain rate loading (e.g. quasi-static loading) [13, 16]. Theoretically, two constant equivalent plastic strain rate experiments are sufficient to determine the other two parameters χ and m^* . They can be found by making a linear fit of the amplitudes of the variable A (let $A = \chi(\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p)^{m^*}$) and equivalent plastic strain rate $\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p$ on the log-log scale. The parameters χ and m^* are determined from the plots as the intercept and the slope, respectively [13].

The associated plastic flow rule is assumed for the plastic evolution in composites. According to this law, the plastic strain rate tensor is expressed as:

$$\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p = \dot{\lambda}^p \partial_{\bar{\sigma}} F \quad (8)$$

where $\dot{\lambda}^p \geq 0$ is a nonnegative plastic consistency parameter; hereafter $\partial_x y = \frac{\partial y}{\partial x}$.

Similarly, the associated hardening rule is also assumed for the equivalent plastic strain rate in the following form:

$$\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}^p = -\dot{\lambda}^p \partial_{\bar{\sigma}} F = \dot{\lambda}^p \quad (9)$$

Note that this form does not hold if the original quadratic form of Thiruppukuzhi and Sun's strain rate-dependent yield criterion is adopted. The use of the associated hardening rule in the form of Eq.(9) reduces computational cost in the numerical integration procedure.

2.3 Damage model

In order to characterise the degradation of material properties due to growth of microcracks after the damage initiation and prior to complete failure of the ply, a CDM-based damage model that has been implemented in the previous version of the elastoplastic damage model [1] is adopted in this work. The damage model includes the damage initiation and propagation criteria, which predict the onset and further evolution of each damage

mechanism, and the damage evolution laws, which govern the evolution of damage variables.

2.3.1 Damage initiation and propagation criteria

In order to predict the damage initiation and propagation of each intralaminar failure mechanism, the damage initiation and propagation criteria are given by

$$f(\phi_I, r_I) = \phi_I - r_I \leq 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\{I = 1t, 1c, 2t, 2c, 6\}$$

where ϕ_I and r_I are the loading function and damage threshold corresponding to each failure mechanism; the loading function ϕ_I is adopted in this work in the form of Hashin's failure criterion [1, 17]; r_I controls the size of the expanding damage surface and depends on the loading history, the initial value of r_I is 1; subscripts 1 and 2 represent the fibre and transverse directions of the unidirectional ply; subscripts t and c denote tension and compression. The damage variable d_6 (see Eq.(4)) represents the damage effects on the shear stiffness due to matrix fracture caused by a combined action of transverse and shear stresses. However, the compressive transverse stress has beneficial effects on the matrix cracking. Thus, it is reasonable to assume that the damage effects are governed by the tensile matrix cracking, i.e. $f_6 = f_{2t}, r_6 = r_{2t}$.

2.3.2 Damage evolution

Once any of the damage initiation and propagation criteria is fulfilled, further loading will cause damage growth leading to the degradation of material stiffness corresponding to the relevant type of failure mechanism. The deterioration of material stiffness is governed by the damage variables. The evolution of damage is possible only when the stresses reach the level corresponding to the damage surface. In further process of damage evolution, the following damage consistency condition should be satisfied to determine the value of the parameter \dot{r}_I

$$\dot{f}_I = \dot{\phi}_I - \dot{r}_I = 0 \quad (11)$$

Based on this condition, the values of the damage thresholds could be found by integrating equation $\dot{r}_I = \dot{\phi}_I$, i.e. $\int_0^t \dot{r}_I dt = \int_0^t \dot{\phi}_I dt$ and taking into account the initial conditions $\phi_{I,0} = 0$ and $r_{I,0} = 1$. The following expressions for damage thresholds r_I can be derived:

$$r_I = \max\{1, \max\{\phi_I^\tau\}\} \quad \tau \in [0, t] \quad (12)$$

The following exponential damage evolution law is adopted for each damage variable to simulate the softening branch of each stress strain curve:

$$d_I = 1 - \frac{1}{r_I} \exp(A_I(1 - r_I)) \quad (13)$$

where A_I is the parameter that defines the exponential damage law. Numerical simulations based on the use of strain-softening material constitutive models might output mesh-dependent results. In order to alleviate the mesh dependency, the parameter A_I is determined using the procedure presented in [1].

3 Computational aspects

The proposed consistency elasto-viscoplastic damage model is implemented in the finite element code Abaqus using the user-defined subroutine UMAT. A strain-driven unconditionally stable implicit numerical integration algorithm based on the closest point projection return mapping procedure for this model is developed. The tangent operator that is consistent with the numerical integration algorithm is also derived to ensure the quadratic convergence rate of the Newton-Raphson method in the nonlinear finite element analysis.

3.1 Integration algorithm

The simulation of plasticity response is an incremental process that must be characterised by the rate constitutive equations (e.g. Eq.(8) and Eq.(9)). To obtain the overall stress strain relationship, the numerical integration of the rate constitutive equations over a discrete sequence of time steps is required. In this way, the continuum problem is converted into a series of incremental problems. The solution of each nonlinear inelastic incremental constitutive problem under consideration is achieved using the Newton-Raphson iterative method, through which the nonlinear incremental problem is consistently linearised into a sequence of linear problems and subsequently solved [18].

The current incremental nonlinear inelastic problem is regarded as strain driven as the stress history is calculated based on the strain history through the integration algorithm. The time history of loading is discretised into a series of time intervals $[t_n, t_{n+1}]$ ($n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$). Within time step

$[t_n, t_{n+1}]$, the strain increment $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and total strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ in UMAT are generated by Abaqus. The initial values of a set of state variables $\{\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_n, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^p, \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_n^p, \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_n, r_{I,n}, d_{I,n}\}$, which are the converged values of the previous increment, are passed on from the main computational procedure. The developed strain-driven implicit integration algorithm is adopted to update this set of state variables as well as the Cauchy stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$. At the end of each increment, the solutions should fulfil all the governing equations that constitute the consistency elasto-viscoplastic damage model. The updated stresses and solution-dependent state variables are stored at the end of the $(n+1)$ th increment and are passed on to the user-defined subroutine UMAT at the beginning of the next increment.

Based on the operator splitting methodology [11], the constitutive equations of the proposed consistency elasto-viscoplastic damage model are additively decomposed into three parts, i.e. the elastic, plastic and damage parts. Accordingly, the numerical integration algorithm consists of three steps, namely, the elastic trial predictor to check the stress state (either plastic loading or unloading), the plastic corrector for iteratively calculating the plastic deformation related internal state variables, such as the plastic strain components, the equivalent plastic strain and its rate, and the damage corrector for calculating the damage variables and the nominal Cauchy stresses. The three-step numerical algorithm is briefly described as follows:

1. The elastic trial predictor

In this step, the mechanical response is assumed to be elastic under the given strain increment $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}$ within $[t_n, t_{n+1}]$. The trial effective stress tensor is calculated as $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} = \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_n + \mathbf{S}(d):\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}$. The plasticity response of the material is assumed to be “frozen”, i.e. the trial plastic strain components and other plastic deformation related internal variables have the values at time t_n . In a similar manner, the damage growth is also assumed to be fixed in this step. The plastic yield criterion Eq.(5) is checked to determine the status of the elastic trial state (the stress state at the current step).

$$F_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} = F(\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}, \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}) \leq 0 \quad (14)$$

Under constant strain rate loading, the value of the equivalent plastic strain rate in the current time

increment is close to that in the previous time increment. In order to improve the efficiency of the algorithm, the converged value of $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p$ at the end of each increment is used as the initial value for the next time increment at the same integration point.

If the plastic yield criterion under the elastic trial state Eq.(14) is satisfied, the elastic trial state lies within or on the yield surface and is the actual stress state within $[t_n, t_{n+1}]$. Otherwise, the elastic trial state lies outside of the yield surface. Plasticity evolves under the given strain increment $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}$. The plastic corrector is used to find the state variables $\{\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{n+1}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p, \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1}^p\}$.

2. The plastic corrector

In the case of plastic loading, the trial effective stresses and plastic internal variables should be corrected to “return” to the yield surface. In this step, the closest point projection return mapping algorithm is employed. The converged values at the end of the $(n+1)$ th increment $\{\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{n+1}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p, \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1}^p\}$ ensure that upon yielding, the determined stress state lies on the yield surface. This prevents the drift from the yield surface due to the unconverged solutions as in the case of explicit integration schemes (such as the forward Euler integration procedure). The nonlinear incremental problem is solved as indicated earlier using Newton-Raphson iterative procedure. The iterations are performed until the final updated set of state variables $\{\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{n+1}^{(k+1)}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}, \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}\}$ fulfils the yield criterion $F(\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_{n+1}^{(k+1)}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}, \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}) \leq \text{TOL}$, where TOL is the error tolerance which is set to 1×10^{-6} in this work.

Until now, the stress state is corrected in the effective space. So only the effective stresses are updated and damage development is not taken into account. In what follows, the corresponding damage variables are updated and the effective stresses are corrected in the damage corrector step to subsequently update the nominal stresses. The final state of the plastic analysis is taken as the initial condition for the damage analysis, while the plastic deformations remain fixed in the damage corrector step.

3. The damage corrector

In the damage corrector step, the damage variables can be determined explicitly using the state variables

obtained from the plastic corrector step. The values of the loading functions $\phi_{l,n+1}$ are calculated according to the Hashin's failure criterion [1] using the updated effective stress components. The trial damage thresholds take the values determined in the previous time step $r_{l,n+1}^{\text{trial}} = r_{l,n}$, and the damage initiation and propagation criteria Eq.(10) $f_l(\phi_{l,n+1}, r_{l,n+1}^{\text{trial}}) \leq 0$ are checked. If the present stress state meets these criteria, damage does not grow and the trial damage thresholds are the actual damage thresholds $r_{l,n+1} = r_{l,n+1}^{\text{trial}} = r_{l,n}$. The corresponding damage variables $d_{l,n+1}$ take the values obtained from the previous time step $d_{l,n}$. Otherwise, damage evolves, according to Eq.(11) and the initial conditions $\phi_{l,0} = 0$, the damage thresholds under the present stress state are determined as $r_{l,n+1} = \phi_{l,n+1}$. Noting that the initial value of each damage threshold is 1.0 and damage growth is an irreversible process, the damage threshold for each damage mechanism is an ever-increasing variable. Therefore, Eq.(12) holds in the loading history. For simplicity, this equation is used directly in the numerical integration algorithm to update the damage thresholds $r_{l,n+1}$. The damage variables for the current state $d_{l,n+1}$ are updated according to Eq.(13). Once the damage variables are determined, the nominal Cauchy stress tensor in the damaged configuration at the end of $(n+1)$ th increment is calculated using the equation Eq.(1) ₂ as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1} = \mathbf{S}(d_{n+1}) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^e \quad (15)$$

The three-step numerical algorithm for the update of stress tensor and solution-dependent state variables (e.g. plastic strains, equivalent plastic strain and its rate) has been implemented in Abaqus using the user-defined material subroutine UMAT. In order to ensure the algorithmic efficiency of the Newton-Raphson method in the implicit finite element analysis, a tangent stiffness operator that is consistent with the developed integration algorithm has been derived and implemented.

3.2 Consistent tangent stiffness tensor

The consistent tangent stiffness tensor provides the relation between a small variation in strain and a small variation in stress around the updated state in which all the governing constitutive equations

remain satisfied at time t_{n+1} . The consistent tangent stiffness tensor for the proposed consistency elasto-viscoplastic damage model is derived in the following form:

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}}{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}} = [\mathbf{M}_{n+1} + \mathbf{S}(d_{n+1})] : \mathbf{C}_0 : \mathbf{S}_{n+1}^{\text{alg}} \quad (16)$$

in which the fourth-order tensor \mathbf{M}_{n+1} can be presented in Voigt notation (in indicial form) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} M_{ik}|_{n+1} &= \left. \frac{\partial S(d)_{ij} \varepsilon_j^e}{\partial \varepsilon_k^e} \right|_{n+1} \\ &= \varepsilon_j^e \left. \frac{\partial S(d)_{ij}}{\partial d_p} \frac{\partial d_p}{\partial r_\xi} \frac{\partial r_\xi}{\partial \phi_\xi} \frac{\partial \phi_\xi}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_q} \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_q}{\partial \varepsilon_k^e} \right|_{n+1} \\ & \quad i, j, p, q, k = \{1, 2, 3\}; \quad \xi = \{1, 2\} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where matrix $\mathbf{M}_{n+1} = [M_{ik}]_{n+1}$ is asymmetric. This results in the asymmetry of the consistent tangent matrix. The explicit expression of matrix \mathbf{M} along with the associated derivatives are given in [1]. In Eq.(16), $\mathbf{C}_0 = \mathbf{S}_0^{-1}$ is the fourth-order compliance tensor of the linear-elastic undamaged composite material and $\mathbf{S}_{n+1}^{\text{alg}}$ is the consistent tangent stiffness tensor for the incremental plastic problem. The latter is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{S}_{n+1}^{\text{alg}} &= \frac{d\bar{\sigma}_{n+1}}{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}} \\ &= \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1} - \frac{(\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1} : \partial_{\bar{\sigma}} F_{n+1}^p) \otimes (\partial_{\bar{\sigma}} F_{n+1} : \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1})}{\partial_{\bar{\sigma}} F_{n+1} : \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1} : \partial_{\bar{\sigma}} F_{n+1}^p - \partial_{\bar{\varepsilon}} p F_{n+1} - \frac{\partial_{\bar{\varepsilon}} p F_{n+1}}{\Delta t}} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1} = (\mathbf{C}_0 + \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p \partial_{\bar{\sigma}\bar{\sigma}}^2 F_{n+1}^p)^{-1}$; $\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p$ denotes the increment of plastic consistent parameter λ^p in the $(n+1)$ th increment; $\partial_{xx}^2 y = \partial^2 y / \partial x^2$; symbol (\otimes) denotes the tensor product of two tensors; Δt is the time increment in the $(n+1)$ th increment, i.e. $\Delta t = t_{n+1} - t_n$, this value is provided by the finite element package Abaqus at the beginning of each time step.

3.3 Viscous regularisation

Numerical simulations based on the implicit procedures, such as Abaqus/Standard, and the use of strain-softening material constitutive models often encounter computational problems and could be aborted prematurely. In order to alleviate these computational difficulties and improve convergence, a viscous regularisation scheme has been implemented in the following form [19]:

$$\dot{d}_m^v = \frac{1}{\eta} (d_m - d_m^v), \quad m = \{1, 2, 3\} \quad (19)$$

where d_m is the damage variable determined according to Eq.(3) and Eq.(4), d_m^v is the regularised viscous damage variable, and η is the viscosity coefficient.

The regularised damage variable in the $(n + 1)$ th increment is calculated as

$$d_{m,n+1}^v = \frac{\Delta t}{\eta + \Delta t} d_{m,n+1} + \frac{\eta}{\eta + \Delta t} d_{m,n}^v \quad (20)$$

and the corresponding regularised consistent tangent stiffness tensor is derived as:

$$\left. \frac{d\sigma_{n+1}}{d\epsilon_{n+1}} \right|_v = [\mathbf{M}_{n+1}^v + \mathbf{S}(d_{n+1}^v)]: \mathbf{C}_0: \mathbf{S}_{n+1}^{\text{alg}} \quad (21)$$

where the fourth-order tensor \mathbf{M}_{n+1}^v can be presented in Voigt notation (in indicial form) as follows:

$$M_{ik}^v|_{n+1} = \left. \frac{\partial S(d^v)_{ij} \epsilon_j^e}{\partial \epsilon_k^e} \right|_{n+1} = \left(\epsilon_j^e \frac{\partial S(d^v)_{ij}}{\partial d_p^v} \frac{\partial d_p}{\partial r_\xi} \frac{\partial r_\xi}{\partial \phi_\xi} \frac{\partial \phi_\xi}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_q} \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_q}{\partial \epsilon_k^e} \right) \Big|_{n+1} \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{\eta + \Delta t} \quad (22)$$

$i, j, p, q, k = \{1, 2, 3\}; \xi = \{1, 2\}$

3.4 Computational procedure

The computational procedure based on the integration algorithm presented earlier includes the computations of the elastic predictor, plastic corrector and damage corrector and the calculation of the regularised consistent tangent stiffness tensor as follows:

1. Initial conditions:

$$\epsilon_{n+1}, \Delta \epsilon_{n+1}, \epsilon_n^p, \tilde{\epsilon}_n^p, \dot{\epsilon}_n^p, \bar{\sigma}_n, \sigma_n, \tilde{\sigma}_n, r_{I,n}, d_{I,n}, d_{m,n}, d_{m,n}^v.$$

2. Elastic predictor:

a. Assign and compute the trial state variables:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}} &= \epsilon_n^p; & \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}} &= \tilde{\epsilon}_n^p; & \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}} &= \dot{\epsilon}_n^p; \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} &= \tilde{\sigma}_n; & \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} &= \bar{\sigma}_n + \mathbf{S}_0: \Delta \epsilon_{n+1}; \end{aligned}$$

b. Check the yield criterion:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} &= F(\bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}, \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}, \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}) \\ &= F^p(\bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}) - \tilde{\sigma}(\tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}, \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}) \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

If $F_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} \leq 0$, then set $\bar{\sigma}_{n+1} = \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}$, $\epsilon_{n+1}^p = \epsilon_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}$, $\tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^p = \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}$, $\dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^p = \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}$, $\tilde{\sigma}_{n+1} = \tilde{\sigma}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}$. Otherwise, plasticity evolves, go to step 3.

3. Plastic corrector (updating the effective Cauchy stresses and plastic internal state variables):

The Newton-Raphson method is employed to solve the nonlinear problem

$$F_{n+1} = F(\bar{\sigma}(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p), \tilde{\epsilon}^p(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p), \dot{\epsilon}^p(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p)) = 0$$

iteratively in order to compute the actual state variables $\{\epsilon_{n+1}^p, \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^p, \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^p, \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}\}$:

a. Initialize:

$$\begin{aligned} k &= 0, & \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{(0)} &= \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}, & \epsilon_{n+1}^{p,(0)} &= \epsilon_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}, \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(0)} &= \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}, & \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(0)} &= \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,\text{trial}}, & \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{p,(0)} &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

b. Calculate $\delta(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)})$, $\delta \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{(k+1)}$, $\delta \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}$, $\delta \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}$, $\delta \epsilon_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}$ in the $(k + 1)$ th iteration;

c. Update the plastic state variables in the $(k+1)$ th iteration:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)} &= \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{p,(k)} + \delta(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}); \\ \epsilon_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)} &= \epsilon_{n+1}^{p,(k)} + \delta \epsilon_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}; \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)} &= \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k)} + \delta \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}; \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)} &= \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k)} + \delta \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}; \\ \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{(k+1)} &= \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{(k)} + \delta \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{(k+1)} \end{aligned}$$

d. Calculate $F_{n+1}^{(k+1)} = F(\bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{(k+1)}, \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}, \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)})$. If $F_{n+1}^{(k+1)} \leq \text{TOL}$, then $\bar{\sigma}_{n+1} = \bar{\sigma}_{n+1}^{(k+1)}$, $\epsilon_{n+1}^p = \epsilon_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}$, $\tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^p = \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}$, $\dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^p = \dot{\epsilon}_{n+1}^{p,(k+1)}$; calculate $\mathbf{S}_{n+1}^{\text{alg}}$. Otherwise, set $k = k + 1$, go to b.

4. Damage corrector (updating the nominal Cauchy stresses):

a. Calculate $\phi_{I,n+1}$, updating $r_{I,n+1} = \max\{1, \phi_{I,n+1}, r_{I,n}\}$

b. Calculate damage variables $d_{I,n+1}$, $d_{m,n+1}$, $d_{m,n+1}^v$ and $\mathbf{S}(d_{n+1}^v)$ with $d_{n+1}^v = \{d_{1,n+1}^v, d_{2,n+1}^v, d_{3,n+1}^v\}^T$.

c. Update the nominal stresses:

$$\sigma_{n+1} = \mathbf{S}(d_{n+1}^v) : (\epsilon_{n+1} - \epsilon_{n+1}^p)$$

d. Calculate the tensor \mathbf{M}_{n+1}^v and the regularised consistent tangent stiffness tensor:

$$\left. \frac{d\sigma_{n+1}}{d\epsilon_{n+1}} \right|_v = [\mathbf{M}_{n+1}^v + \mathbf{S}(d_{n+1}^v)]: \mathbf{C}_0: \mathbf{S}_{n+1}^{\text{alg}}$$

This procedure has been implemented in Abaqus using the user-defined material subroutine UMAT.

4 Numerical Analyses

To examine the capability of the proposed methodology of capturing the rate dependent response and predicting the failure of composite laminates, the progressive failure analyses of S2/8552 composite laminates with layups $[\pm 45^\circ/90_2]_{4s}$ and $[75_2^\circ/-60^\circ/30^\circ]_{4s}$ subjected to uniaxial tensile loading at strain rates of 0.0001, 0.01, and 1/s in the length direction have been performed. The experimental investigation of the mechanical response of these laminates was carried out by Tsai and Wang [20]. The length, width and thickness of the laminates are 100, 17.8 and 2.4 mm, respectively. The material properties and model parameters of S2/8552 composite reported in Tsai and Wang [20] are adopted in these analyses and listed in Table 1.

Strain rate-independent longitudinal tensile strength s_{1t} is adopted for S2/8552 composites with the value of 2006 MPa for a similar S2-glass/epoxy composite material system as reported in [21]. The dynamic longitudinal compressive strengths s_{1c} are determined based on the results of experiments conducted by Tsai and Sun [22]. According to the investigations published in [23-26], a unified logarithmic function having the same form as that reported in [26] is developed for the prediction of the strain rate-dependent matrix dominated strengths in the following form:

$$s(\dot{\epsilon}) = s(\dot{\epsilon}_0) \left(m_s \log \frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\dot{\epsilon}_0} + 1 \right) \quad (23)$$

where parameter s represents s_{2t} , s_{2c} , and s_s ; m_s is material parameter that is determined from curve fitting of experimental data, and $\dot{\epsilon}_0$ is the reference strain rate, which takes the value of $10^{-4}/s$ for quasi-static loading. For S2/8552 glass/epoxy composite, the transverse tensile strength $s_{2t}(\dot{\epsilon}_0) = 131$ MPa as reported in [25], the transverse compressive strength $s_{2c}(\dot{\epsilon}_0) = 242.27$ MPa, while the value of the in-plane shear strength $s_s(\dot{\epsilon}_0) = 87.79$ MPa. The value of the material parameter m_s is determined to be 0.08926. In this work, constant values of strengths are used in the analyses during the loading history. The corresponding results for each strain rate are listed in Table 2.

The values of fracture toughness parameters associated with fibre tensile and compressive failure $G_{1t,c} = 81.5$ N/mm and $G_{1c,c} = 106.3$ N/mm for IM7/8552 reported in [27] are adopted in this study. The value of Mode I dynamic initiation interlaminar fracture toughness of S2/8552 composites given as 1.2395 N/mm in [28] is used as a substitution for the Mode I intralaminar fracture toughness parameter $G_{2t,c}$. The parameter $G_{6,c} = 2.5459$ N/mm as measured by Bing and Sun [29]. Using this value, the parameter $G_{2c,c}$ is calculated according to the equation suggested in [30], i.e. $G_{2c,c} = G_{6,c}/\cos(53^\circ) = 4.2304$ N/mm. These parameters are listed in Table 1.

The comparisons of the experimental and predicted uniaxial stress versus strain curves calculated for the S2/8552 glass/epoxy laminates with the layups of $[\pm 45^\circ/90_2]_{4s}$ and $[75_2^\circ/-60^\circ/30^\circ]_{4s}$ loaded at three different strain rates are depicted in Figs. 1 and 2. It follows from these graphs that the strain rate-dependent mechanical response of S2/8552 composites is well reflected. The model predictions agree reasonably well with the experimental results at strain levels less than 1%. Discrepancies become larger at higher strain levels. As can be seen, the failure behaviour of the composite laminates could be predicted by the present model sufficiently well. It follows from Figs. 1 and 2 that more significant stress drops are observed in the $[\pm 45^\circ/90_2]_{4s}$ laminates compared with those shown for the $[75_2^\circ/-60^\circ/30^\circ]_{4s}$ laminates. This is because only the fibres in the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies of the $[\pm 45^\circ/90_2]_{4s}$ laminates contribute to resistance of the uniaxial loading. Whereas in the case of the $[75_2^\circ/-60^\circ/30^\circ]_{4s}$ laminates, the fibres in all the plies are carrying the load. As a consequence, the failure processes in the $[\pm 45^\circ/90_2]_{4s}$ laminates are more abrupt. A minor stress decrease is first observed in each uniaxial stress versus strain curve of a $[\pm 45^\circ/90_2]_{4s}$ laminate and then followed by a more pronounced stress drop. The first drop is triggered by the matrix cracking in the 90° plies while the second one is caused by matrix cracking occurring in the 45° plies. According to the predicted pattern of damage development (i.e. variations in d_1 and d_2 parameters), the failure modes in these two laminates can be attributed to matrix cracking. The matrix damage distribution at the end of the analysis in a 30° ply of the $[75_2^\circ/-60^\circ/30^\circ]_{4s}$ S2/8552

glass/epoxy laminate subjected to tensile loading at a strain rate of 1/s is illustrated in Fig. 3. It follows from this figure that matrix damage spreads in a large area of the ply. The matrix damage patterns in other plies of the $[75_2^{\circ}/-60^{\circ}/30^{\circ}]_{4s}$ laminate are similar to the one shown in Fig. 3. For both laminates under consideration, the fibre breakage has not been observed. As can be seen from Figs. 1 and 2, the damage progression occurs without further increase in the external loading when the certain level of matrix damage in the laminates has been reached.

5. Conclusions

A consistency elasto-viscoplastic damage model capable of simulating the strain rate-dependent behaviour and progressive failure of composite laminates has been developed. The model takes into account various failure mechanisms, strain rate-dependent effects and the progressive degradation of material stiffnesses. The corresponding strain-driven implicit numerical integration algorithm employing the closest point projection return mapping algorithm has been developed for the solution of the nonlinear problems under consideration. The tangent stiffness operator that is consistent with the developed numerical integration procedure has also been derived to ensure the quadratic convergence rate pertaining to the Newton-Raphson method in the finite element analysis of nonlinear problems. The material model has been verified through numerical simulations of S2/8552 laminates with two different layups which exhibit significant strain-rate dependent response under tensile loading at various strain rates. It has been shown that the proposed model is capable of efficiently capturing the strain-rate dependent mechanical response of composite materials and predicting their failure sufficiently well.

Table 1: Material properties of S2/8552 and model parameters

E_1^0	E_2^0	G_{12}^0	ν_{12}^0	a	χ	m^*
55.7 GPa	21.5 GPa	6.9 GPa	0.29	1.4	$6.50e-12$ (MPa) ^{-n*}	-0.125
n^*	$G_{1t,c}$	$G_{1c,c}$	$G_{2t,c}$	$G_{2c,c}$	$G_{6,c}$	
3.9	81.5 N/mm	106.3 MPa	1.2395 N/mm	4.2304 N/mm	2.5459 N/mm	

Table 2: Dynamic strengths of S2-glass/epoxy composite laminates subjected to various loading rates

Strain rate	0.0001/s	0.01/s	1/s
S_{1t}	2006	2006	2006
S_{1c}	897.36	1098.70	1300.03
S_{2t}	131.00	154.39	177.77
S_{2c}	242.27	285.52	328.77
S_5	87.79	103.46	119.13

Fig. 1. Comparison of the predicted and experimental uniaxial stress versus strain curves of the $[\pm 45^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_{2s}$ S2/8552 glass/epoxy composite laminates subjected to tensile loading at strain rates of 0.0001/s, 0.01/s and 1/s.

Fig. 2. Comparison of the predicted and experimental uniaxial stress versus strain curves of the $[75^{\circ}/-60^{\circ}/30^{\circ}]_{4s}$ S2/8552 glass/epoxy laminates subjected to tensile loading at strain rates of 0.0001/s, 0.01/s and 1/s.

Fig. 3. Predicted matrix damage pattern (d_2) at the end of the analysis in a 30° ply of the $[75^\circ/-60^\circ/30^\circ]_{4s}$ S2/8552 glass/epoxy laminate subjected to tensile loading at a strain rate of 1/s.

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